

1 **AffectiveCNN: MATLAB Software Pipeline for Affective Tactile Gesture Recognition**
2 **Using Compact 1D Convolutional Neural Networks**

3
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8
9 **Abstract**

10 *We present an end-to-end MATLAB pipeline for developing, training, and evaluating compact*
11 *1D convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for affective tactile gesture recognition. The pipeline*
12 *spans Bluetooth-based sensor data acquisition, signal quality control, interactive latency*
13 *truncation, sliding-window segmentation with optional loop-based augmentation, and automated*
14 *multi-architecture hyperparameter sweeping via MATLAB Experiment Manager. A symbolic*
15 *domain-specific language enables rapid specification and large-scale comparison of CNN*
16 *topologies. The final stage displays real-time classification likelihoods from live sensor data*
17 *streamed from a physical sensorized device via Bluetooth. The software is implemented in*
18 *MATLAB R2025a, released under the MIT License, and available at GitHub and Zenodo.*

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20 **Keywords**

21 *affective computing; tactile gesture recognition; 1D convolutional neural networks; MATLAB;*
22 *human-robot interaction; socially assistive robots*

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25 **Metadata**

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Nr	Code metadata description	Metadata
C1	Current code version	v2.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/aleksandrs-v/affective_cnn
C3	Permanent link to reproducible capsule	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17650545
C4	Legal code license	MIT License
C5	Code versioning system used	Git
C6	Software code languages, tools and services used	MATLAB, Processing (Java); MATLAB Deep Learning Toolbox, MATLAB Experiment Manager
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments and dependencies	MATLAB R2025a or later, Deep Learning Toolbox; Windows / macOS / Linux
C8	If available, link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/aleksandrs-v/affective_cnn/blob/main/README.md
C9	Support email for questions	Aleksandrs.Valisevskis@rtu.lv

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28 **1. Motivation and significance**

29 Physical touch is a primary channel through which humans communicate affective intent [1],
30 and equipping socially assistive robots (SARs) with the capacity to perceive and classify tactile
31 gestures has become an increasingly active area of human-robot interaction (HRI) research [2].
32 For a SAR to respond appropriately to gestures such as stroking, patting, or squeezing, it must

33 reliably infer the emotional meaning of contact from raw sensor data collected under conditions
34 of natural, unscripted interaction.

35 The direct impetus for this software arose during the development of a soft sensorized
36 companion designed for therapeutic sessions with children affected by Autism spectrum
37 disorder (ASD) [3]. The first iteration of the companion's gesture recognition module operated
38 on a heuristic rule-based algorithm that encoded manually defined thresholds over sensor
39 magnitude and duration, supplemented by frequency-domain features. While this approach
40 could coarsely separate active contact from rest, it failed to reliably differentiate between subtle
41 gestures, particularly when gestures involved similar movements. This failure made the case for
42 replacing the heuristic rule-based module with an ML-based gesture recognition system capable
43 of learning discriminative, user-invariant representations directly from raw time-series signals.

44 Designing such a system in practice requires navigating a sequence of non-trivial engineering
45 tasks: acquiring and storing multi-participant recordings from a custom Bluetooth sensor
46 interface, removing reaction-time latency from gesture onset, segmenting variable-length
47 recordings into fixed-width training windows without distorting short periodic signals or losing
48 information contained in longer signals, efficiently searching across convolutional neural
49 network (CNN) architecture variants before committing to a final model. Prior work has
50 demonstrated the effectiveness of deep neural networks for social and affective touch
51 recognition [4, 5, 6], and 1D CNNs in particular have emerged as a strong choice for time-series
52 classification tasks [7]. However, these contributions typically report experimental results without
53 releasing the accompanying data preparation and training infrastructure, leaving practitioners to
54 reconstruct the pipeline independently.

55 MATLAB was selected as the primary implementation platform for two complementary reasons.
56 First, its interactive script-based environment is well suited to the exploratory, iterative nature of
57 sensor-interface development and signal processing research. Second, neural networks trained
58 in MATLAB can be converted to C/C++ source code via MATLAB Coder, providing a viable
59 pathway toward future integration with dedicated hardware. The data acquisition module, which
60 communicates with the physical sensorized device over a Bluetooth serial link, was
61 implemented in Processing (Java), adapted from an open-source gesture recording tool [8].

62 This paper describes the complete software pipeline and its constituent modules. The pipeline
63 was employed to design and validate the compact 1D CNN architecture reported in the
64 companion publication [9], where it achieved high classification accuracy. The pipeline is
65 published as open-source software [10]. The generated dataset is publicly available on Zenodo
66 under a FAIR-compliant release [11].

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68 **2. Software description**

69 **2.1. Software architecture**

70 The pipeline consists of seven modules arranged in a strictly sequential processing chain
71 (Figure 1). One module – the data acquisition tool – is implemented in the Processing (Java)
72 environment; the remaining six are standard MATLAB scripts or MATLAB Experiment Manager
73 Live Scripts. Each module reads its input from disk and writes its output back to disk as
74 structured .csv or .mat files, so processing can be resumed from any stage without rerunning
75 upstream steps, and individual modules can be replaced or adapted independently. Two stages
76 – signal truncation and real-time classification – present graphical user interfaces (GUIs) rather
77 than batch execution, reflecting the inherently interactive nature of those tasks: truncation
78 requires human judgment about gesture onset on a per-recording basis, and real-time
79 observation is by definition a live, exploratory activity.

80 Stage 1 is Processing (Java). Stages 2 through 5 are plain MATLAB scripts with no deep-
 81 learning dependency. Stage 6 includes a script for manual testing of different architectures, as
 82 well as fully prepared and configured scripts for the MATLAB Experiment Manager (included
 83 with the Deep Learning Toolbox) for automatic sweeping through parameters. Stage 7 requires
 84 a trained *.mat* model file produced by Stage 6. The complete pipeline runs on any OS that
 85 supports Processing and MATLAB R2025a with the Deep Learning Toolbox; no additional
 86 toolboxes are required.

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89 *Figure 1. End-to-end software pipeline for affective tactile gesture recognition. Stages are colour-coded*
 90 *by implementation language. Intermediate artefacts (.csv, .mat) are shown between stages.*

91 2.2. Software functionalities

92 Stage 1 – Data Acquisition (PlushSamples.pde, Processing)

93 The acquisition module is a graphical Processing application adapted from an open-source
 94 gesture recording tool [8]. It opens a Bluetooth serial connection to the sensorized device and
 95 reads incoming frames. Each frame is a newline-terminated string of 14 integers: a cumulative
 96 capacitive signal across all sensing electrodes (channel 1), nine individual capacitive sensor
 97 channels (channels 2–10), three accelerometer axes in X, Y, Z order (channels 11–13), and the
 98 delay since the previous frame in milliseconds (channel 14). A 20-second rolling visualisation
 99 window displays all channels in real time (Figure 2). Gesture recordings are triggered by
 100 pressing the spacebar; a three-second countdown precedes capture, allowing the operator to
 101 establish the gesture before logging begins. Output files are timestamped *.csv* files written to a
 102 configurable directory, with gesture class labels encoded in the filename according to a user-
 103 defined GESTURES array.

104 In the companion study, the acquisition tool was configured for 17 gesture classes
 105 corresponding to distinct affective touch patterns performed by human participants. An 18th
 106 class ("At rest") was recorded separately using the same tool without human interaction. This
 107 yielded the full 18-class taxonomy used in all subsequent pipeline stages.

Figure 2. Gesture Recorder tool used to collect training data.

Stage 2 – Organisation and Pseudonymisation (a_move_labelled_data.m)

Raw session files are reorganised from a person-centric directory layout into a class-centric layout expected by all downstream scripts. For each file, the first numeric token in the filename – which identifies the recording session – is replaced with a randomly generated seven-digit integer, breaking any link between the file and its source session while preserving the gesture class label in the filename. This produces the “Training Data - labelled” directory tree consumed by Stages 3–5.

Stage 3 – Quality Control (b_training_data_analysis.m)

The QC module computes per-class summary statistics – mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum recording length – and identifies outliers as any sample whose length deviates from the class mean by more than a configurable fraction (default thresholdRange = 0.4, i.e. $\pm 40\%$). All samples for each class are plotted automatically, with outliers appearing on a separate plot (Figure 3), enabling the researcher to make informed inclusion or exclusion decisions rather than applying blind automated filtering.

Figure 3. Examples of outliers' visualizations by the QC routine.

Stage 4 – Interactive Truncation (c_training_data_truncation.m)

The script's primary design goal is throughput: a realistic dataset collected from multiple participants may yield hundreds or even thousands of individual recordings, making manual truncation in external tools such as spreadsheet software entirely impractical. The script addresses this by providing a graphical user interface (GUI) window that reduces each

131 truncation decision to two actions: a single click on the displayed signal waveform to mark the
132 onset of intentional contact, followed by pressing Enter to confirm and advance to the next
133 recording (Figure 4). In practice, this workflow allows the researcher to review and truncate
134 each recording in a few seconds, making it feasible to process collections of several hundred
135 samples in a single session.

136 The script operates in two sequential phases. Phase 1 runs the GUI review session described
137 above. In Phase 2, the saved decision file is read and each recording is truncated accordingly;
138 original files are preserved in a timestamped backup directory before being overwritten with the
139 truncated versions. Because reaction-time latency is subject- and trial-specific, this step cannot
140 be replaced by a fixed-offset rule without introducing systematic bias into training data.

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Figure 4. Interactive tool for truncating the initial portion of data samples.

143 **Stage 5 – Windowing and Augmentation (d_data_preparation.m)**

144 Before windowing, the 13 raw sensor columns are reduced to 11 features: the three
145 accelerometer axes (X, Y, Z) are replaced by their vector magnitude, yielding a single inertial
146 channel that is orientation-invariant. The processed recordings are split into training, validation,
147 and test subsets in a 70/15/15 ratio using stratified sampling.

148 The script offers two user-selectable windowing modes. The default mode extracts fixed-length
149 windows of 250 samples (2.5 s at 100 Hz) using a sliding window with a 50-sample hop stride,
150 generating multiple overlapping training instances per recording and ensuring that no collected
151 signal data is discarded. An alternative mode pads all recordings to a uniform length using cyclic
152 repetition rather than zero-padding, preserving the spectral characteristics of short periodic
153 gestures. The user selects the mode by executing the corresponding script section. The output
154 is a labelled tensor ready for direct ingestion by Stage 6.

155 **Stage 6 – Architecture Search and Training (Experiment Manager + e_train.m)**

156 Network architectures are specified via a compact symbolic domain-specific language: a string
157 such as 14d1_39d2_41d4 defines a three-layer dilated 1D CNN in which the first convolutional
158 layer uses a kernel of width 14 at dilation factor 1, the second a kernel of width 39 at dilation 2,
159 and the third a kernel of width 41 at dilation 4. Filter counts are controlled independently through
160 a global filter-scaling multiplier, which constitutes a separate axis of the hyperparameter sweep.
161 Each convolutional layer is followed by layer normalisation and a ReLU activation; a global
162 average pooling layer and a fully connected softmax output head complete the network. The
163 architecture string is parsed at runtime by PlushCNNExperiment.mlx, which constructs the

164 corresponding MATLAB network graph and dispatches training via MATLAB Experiment
165 Manager.

166 The systematic sweep conducted for the companion study covered 468 trials across 13
167 architecture strings, 4 filter-scaling multipliers, 3 epoch counts, and 3 batch sizes, running
168 without manual intervention beyond initial configuration. All trained networks, their learning
169 curves, and per-epoch validation metrics remain accessible in the Experiment Manager
170 workspace. The metric_Accuracy.mlx script evaluates any selected model on the held-out test
171 partition. For targeted single-architecture experiments, e_train.m provides a self-contained
172 training path supporting dilated 1D CNNs.

173 **Stage 7 – Real-time PC Simulation (f_realtime_classifier.m)**

174 The script launches a graphical user interface (GUI) window (Figure 5) and streams live sensor
175 data from the physical device via a Bluetooth serial connection (COM port and baud rate are
176 configurable parameters). Incoming frames are read into a ring buffer; once the buffer is filled to
177 250 samples, inference is run on the current window using the loaded .mat model. The
178 inference stride – defaulting to 50 samples – and the display refresh rate – defaulting to every
179 50 received lines – are independently configurable parameters.

180 The GUI shows a live bar chart of per-class likelihoods updated at the configured refresh rate,
181 alongside the top prediction label and its confidence score, and a secondary plot of the most
182 recent sensor window. The module produces no output files: the researcher observes classifier
183 behaviour directly and uses these observations to inform subsequent validation or model
184 selection decisions.

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Figure 5. GUI of a real-time gesture classifier.

187 **3. Illustrative examples**

188 This section walks through a representative end-to-end execution of the pipeline, from raw data
189 ingestion to real-time classification, using the dataset collected for the companion study [9]. The
190 dataset comprises recordings from 25 participants across three age groups (children,

191 teenagers, adults), covering an 18-class taxonomy of affective tactile gestures – 17 classes of
192 human-performed gestures including strokes, scratches, taps, hits, holds, and pulls applied to
193 different body regions of the sensorized companion, plus an 'At rest' baseline class recorded by
194 placing the device in various static orientations without human contact.

195 **Organising files and running the quality control stage.**

196 After organising the collected CSV files with a_move_labelled_data.m, the researcher executes
197 b_training_data_analysis.m. The script iterates over all gesture classes in “Training Data -
198 labelled” and produces a per-class statistical summary table. For each class, all individual
199 recordings are plotted as overlaid duration bars, with samples flagged as outliers (deviating
200 more than the set threshold from the class mean) rendered in a distinct colour. In the
201 companion study, this step identified a small number of recordings interrupted by device
202 disconnection mid-gesture; these were removed before proceeding to truncation.

203 **Interactive truncation session.**

204 Executing c_training_data_truncation.m opens the truncation GUI. For each recording in
205 sequence, the researcher observes the first sensor channel, clicks on the waveform at the point
206 where intentional contact begins – typically visible as the first sustained deflection from baseline
207 – and presses Enter to confirm and advance to the next file. Backspace allows returning to a
208 previous recording for correction. After reviewing all recordings, S saves the decisions and
209 Phase 2 runs automatically: all files are backed up and truncated in batch.

210 **Windowed dataset preparation.**

211 Running d_data_preparation.m converts the truncated recordings into a uniformly structured
212 tensor. For a gesture class such as "Back stroke" – a smooth, sustained contact pattern lasting
213 3–5 s – the sliding-window procedure generates several overlapping 2.5 s windows per
214 recording, effectively augmenting the training set without synthesising artificial data. Even
215 shorter impulsive gestures such as "Tail tap" yield at least one valid window, since the hop
216 stride ensures that available signal content is captured. If the alternative loop-padding mode is
217 selected instead, short recordings are extended by cyclic repetition, retaining the temporal
218 pattern of the original gesture rather than introducing a silent zero-padded tail.

219 **Architecture sweep and model selection.**

220 After configuring the architecture list and hyperparameter grid in
221 PlushCNNExperimentInitialization.mlx, the Experiment Manager dispatches all 468 trials. Upon
222 completion, the researcher sorts the results table in the Experiment Manager workspace by
223 accuracy and selects the best-performing architecture in terms of size and accuracy. In the
224 companion study, the 14d1_39d2_41d4 topology with an appropriate filter multiplier achieved
225 the best balance of accuracy and parameter count (13,200 parameters, 85% mean LOSO-CV
226 accuracy) and was selected for real-time observation.

227 **Real-time observation.**

228 Loading the selected .mat model into f_realtime_classifier.m and connecting the physical
229 sensorized device opens the live classifier GUI. During the companion study's real-time session,
230 five participants performed each gesture class; the per-class likelihood bar chart updated at
231 approximately 2 Hz (50-sample inference stride at 100 Hz), and EMA smoothing visibly
232 stabilised the displayed probabilities. The session confirmed that the selected model produced
233 consistent, gesture-specific activations across new users within approximately 2.0–2.4 s of
234 gesture onset.

235 **4. Impact**

236 **Enabling end-to-end development without infrastructure assembly.**

237 Researchers working on affective touch recognition with custom or commercial sensorized
238 devices typically face a fragmented development landscape: data acquisition, quality control,
239 preprocessing, and real-time observation are handled by separate, unconnected tools – or
240 implemented ad hoc for each project. The present pipeline integrates all of these stages in a
241 single sequential framework, reducing the time between initial data collection and a working,
242 observable classifier. Two stages of the pipeline present dedicated GUI windows – the
243 truncation curator and the real-time classifier – reducing the need for manual configuration and
244 making the most judgment-dependent steps of the workflow accessible to researchers without
245 deep programming expertise. This should be particularly useful for groups whose primary
246 expertise is in affective computing or human-robot interaction rather than software engineering.

247 **Supporting systematic architecture comparison.**

248 The symbolic CNN architecture Domain-Specific Language (DSL) and its integration with
249 MATLAB Experiment Manager lower the barrier to large-scale architecture search for
250 practitioners who have not previously worked with automated hyperparameter optimisation. In
251 the companion study, 468 candidate architectures were evaluated without writing custom
252 training loops or result-aggregation scripts – a scope of search that would be impractical to
253 conduct manually. The unified Experiment Manager workspace, in which all trained models and
254 their metrics are simultaneously accessible, further supports exploratory post-hoc analysis: a
255 researcher can sort, filter, and compare results, then load any candidate model directly into the
256 real-time simulation stage within the same session.

257 **Closing the gap between training and real-world observation.**

258 The real-time classification GUI allows a trained model to be observed against live, naturalistic
259 sensor data from the physical device immediately after training – without any intermediary
260 export, format conversion, or hardware programming step. The per-class likelihood display
261 provides direct behavioural feedback on the trained model and informs model selection before
262 any further integration steps are undertaken. Such rapid feedback is difficult to achieve with
263 general-purpose ML frameworks, which do not natively handle serial sensor streaming or
264 provide a live probability visualisation tied directly to the trained model object.

265 **Pathway toward hardware integration.**

266 Because the pipeline is implemented entirely in MATLAB, trained networks can be converted to
267 C/C++ source code using MATLAB Coder without rewriting the inference logic. This provides a
268 direct route from the training environment to microcontroller targets – a step that in alternative
269 frameworks would require a separate export and conversion workflow. The companion study
270 confirmed that the selected model's computational cost is theoretically compatible with inference
271 on an ESP32-class microcontroller.

272 **Generalisability beyond the original application.**

273 Although the pipeline was developed in the context of a specific sensorized companion, its
274 configurable stages are not tied to that hardware. The only requirement is a data communication
275 channel and sensors that can be used for classification. The acquisition module exposes a
276 configurable gesture label array and serial port parameters; the preprocessing and training
277 stages operate on any multichannel time-series CSV with a compatible column structure.
278 Researchers working with other Bluetooth-streamed tactile or inertial sensor arrays – for
279 example in wearables, prosthetics, or other HRI platforms – can adapt the pipeline with
280 adjustments limited to a small number of configuration variables.

281 **Availability and usage.**

282 The software is publicly available at https://github.com/aleksandrs-v/affective_cnn under the MIT
283 License, with a permanent archive at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17650545>. The package is
284 being released publicly together with this article; external usage metrics will accumulate through
285 Zenodo download statistics and GitHub activity following publication.

286 **5. Conclusions**

287 This paper describes an open-source, end-to-end MATLAB software pipeline for the
288 development, systematic evaluation, and real-time PC-based observation of compact 1D
289 convolutional neural networks applied to affective tactile gesture recognition. The pipeline
290 covers the complete workflow from Bluetooth-streamed data acquisition through interactive
291 quality control and preprocessing to large-scale automated architecture search and live sensor-
292 driven inference, with all stages implemented as modular scripts that can be adapted or
293 extended independently.

294 The pipeline was used to design and validate the model reported in the companion publication
295 [9], demonstrating its practical utility on a real 18-class affective touch dataset collected from 25
296 participants. Its principal contributions – the symbolic CNN architecture DSL, the GUI-based
297 interactive truncation tool, the sliding-window augmentation strategy, and the live real-time
298 classifier GUI – address recurring practical challenges that are absent from general-purpose
299 machine learning frameworks.

300

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303 source GestureRecorder Processing application by Jon E. Froehlich and the Makeability Lab at
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309 real-world data.

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316

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